

THE INTERPENETRATION OF ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

Solijonov Muxammadjon Zokirjon o'g'li

Scientific supervisor: Students of the Faculty of "Russian language and Literature"

Kimsanova Madinaxon Sherzod qizi

Abrorjonova Gulzodaxon Abrorjon qizi

Abdumutaliyev Abduxalok Xolboyzoda

Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Kokand city.

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Annotation: The article highlights the problems of the correlation of Russian and English languages. In this article, the impact of socio-cultural factors on the formation of trends in the mutual use of English and Russian languages is subjected to research and careful consideration. The current period could not but leave its imprint on the formation of cultures and the development of languages of Western civilizations: many concepts that turned out to be more accurate and accurate or which for some reason simply did not exist in the future recipient language eventually became fixed as international concepts.

Key words: language, culture, mutual enrichment, borrowing

Language is a living, dynamic, developing matter, it easily adapts to any situation, providing for the needs of a person. Recently, the process of language development and mutual enrichment of languages of different peoples has become more and more rapid. One of the most popular ways of enrichment is borrowing. The appearance of new words in the recipient language makes it easy to fill in the formed language gaps.

First of all, considering Russian and English directly, it is worth talking about the peculiarities of each of them. Russian, in the words of the famous Russian classic, "great and mighty", extremely rich, but even in such a language, for example, borrowings are not rare, which is explained by the need to replenish the language with new means. "All this is natural, since the language itself has always developed and functioned in the context of culture..." [6, p. 143]. The peculiarity of the English-speaking culture is its multicultural nature. Thus, having received the status of the language of international communication, the English language spreads at lightning speed and penetrates into the lexicon of other peoples, nations. The Russian language has not passed this process either.

The reasons for borrowing can be such as the historical factor (direct contacts of countries and peoples within the framework of cultural and historical mutual influence and interpenetration); linguistic economy, rationality; lack of names of objects, objects and processes in the language; imitation and following fashionable linguistic trends.

Sometimes the Russian language also faces the problem of the lack of the most precise and specific concept for a particular object. An example is a borrowed and frequently used word «бестселлер», denoting the "best-selling book". In this case, Anglicism turned out to be more capacious for naming a specific concept. Currently, it should be noted the phenomenal expansion of Anglicisms in such areas as "Politics" ("speechwriter", "summit", "speaker"), "Economics" ("marketing", "broker", "business"). And as for sports topics, there are equivalents of such words in the Russian language.

At the turn of the XX–XXI centuries, the English-speaking world established itself on the world stage as a leader in the industry of modern computer technologies. In the conditions of computerization, as well as the rapid development of information technologies in general, the

need for naming new objects and phenomena is most acute. So, the Russian language from English includes words such as "компьютер", "браузер", "принтер", "скриншот", etc. Youth slang has long included in its arsenal such borrowings as "постить" (to post on the Internet), «комменты» (comments), "гуглить" (search) and many others. It is noteworthy that such borrowed words as "компьютер" or, for example, "брокер" in Russian acquire broad derivative abilities. They easily form relative adjectives with the help of suffixes -н(ый), -ов(ый), -ск(ий) [5, p. 54]. For example, компьютер – компьютерный, маркетинг – маркетинговый, брокер – брокерский.

In addition, the process of morphemization is familiar in Russian culture, that is, the formation of certain foreign-language structural components as independent morphemes. Often, the Russian language adopts some foreign word-forming elements (prefixes, suffixes) and correlates them with its own language models and structures. As an example, we can take the word «экс-чиновник» with the prefix from the English language – ex.

It should also be noted that "linguists suggest that such a massive invasion of English vocabulary and its subsequent development cause a restructuring of the morphological system and the emergence of analytical trends in the syntax of the host language" [3, pp. 178-179]. So, some syntactic constructions entered the Russian language and turned out to be very productive in terms of word formation. In an analytical way – that is, a way of adding two bases that does not undergo morphological changes – such words as, for example, «рок-музыка», «поп-культура», «Интернет-провод», etc. were created.

The media abound in foreign language implementations, aiming to provide a certain stylistic effect that should attract the attention of readers, viewers or listeners. For example, in a number of articles correspondents and journalists prefer to use the buzzword "super" [1,2,4]. In Uzbekistan, since the end of the last century, there has been an extraordinary interest in Western culture, which is reflected in the constant borrowing of ideas, words and style of behavior in everyday life. This explains the popularization of foreign inclusions in articles and notes. As you know, such a social group as youth is most susceptible to changes, including various youth movements and organizations that are most susceptible to any language innovations and fall under the influence of fashion. Also, the reason for the stable use of Anglicisms among young people is that young people tend to join the American culture and lifestyle, which are particularly popular, thanks to the established stereotype of an idealized American society with a high standard of living, democratic values. An example are the following words and phrases: "battle", "respect", "happy end", which entered the Russian language in the eighties-nineties of the XX century and were fixed in it in its original form, taking into account phonetic changes caused by the phonetic structure of the language.

The lack of equivalents is one of the leading reasons for borrowing. It is this problem that contributes to the acquisition of new vocabulary in the English language. At the end of the XX – beginning of the XXI century, several Russian-language words entered the English language. The English language borrowed words such as "glasnost", "perestroika". Also, over time, words such as "gopnik" and "silovik" entered the English language, reflecting changes of a socio-political nature [7, 8]. As for the last word, the Russian version of the singular and plural endings (silovik – siloviki) has entered the English language. And, for example, the Russian word "бабушка" has passed into English with the English version of the formation of the plural ending of nouns (babushka – babushkas).

Let's turn to such a method of translation as "calculus". Elements of Russian words and expressions were literally translated into English (palace of culture – дом культуры, five-year-plan – пятилетка). Note at the same time that much more often the recipient language tries to find the most suitable, close verbal equivalent that already exists in a particular language. For example, the Russian word «единоличник» in English is explained as "individual peasant", «воскресник» – as "voluntary Sunday". It is important to mention here that both of these methods of translating other people's words and expressions should be distinguished, because their final result is different from each other: that is, when selecting a certain equivalent, approximate to the general meaning of the borrowed phenomenon and more native and understandable for native speakers, with this type of translation, there is no increase in the dictionary, while calculus replenishes the language with new vocabulary units. Russian Russian, but in general, it is worth noting that the proportion of borrowings from English to Russian and from Russian to English varies significantly.

Thus, we can see by illustrative examples how mutual enrichment, interpenetration of languages and cultures occurs under the influence of changes in various spheres of public life. And it is very important that through borrowing, calculus, and the spread of word-formation and syntactic models, penetrating words cease to be alien. That is why such a phenomenon as the mutual enrichment of languages can be attributed to natural interlanguage processes that have a direct impact on the cultural component of any society.

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